

FEATURES OF THE TREATMENT OF PULPITIS IN CHILDREN**Mammadova S.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor
Department of Therapeutik Dentistry***Ashrafov D.***Department of Orthopedic Dentistry Assistant***Kalbiyeva N.***Department of Pediatry Dentistry Assistant**Azerbaijan Medical University**Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14003940>

Despite numerous studies conducted in different countries, the treatment of complications of dental caries, in particular pulpitis, remains an important and pressing problem in pediatric dentistry. Treatment of dental pulpitis in children is a complex and responsible task in the practical work of a dentist, whose goal is to quickly eliminate pain, prevent the development of the inflammatory process in the periodontium of the tooth and preserve its functional value. Existing methods of treating pulpitis of primary teeth can be divided into conservative, aimed at preserving the vitality (viability) of the entire pulp, and surgical, involving the removal of either its coronal part (amputation or pulpotomy) or the entire pulp (extirpation or pulpectomy). In turn, surgical methods can be performed under anesthesia - vital amputation, vital extirpation or after preliminary devitalization - devital amputation, devital extirpation. Modern approaches to the treatment of pulpitis in primary teeth provide for the possibility of one-session treatment with final restoration of the tooth in one visit. At the same time, the amputation method has remained the most controversial for decades. Today there is a discussion both about the very feasibility of using the amputation method and about the preparation for covering the root pulp stump. The list of alternative methods for vital pulpotomy of primary teeth includes the use of formocresol (Spedding, Regidig, 1968; Loos, Hans 1973; Fuks, Bistein, 1981), 4% glutaraldehyde buffer solution (Ranly, Lazzary, 1978), calcium hydroxide (Tenschler, Zander, 1938 ; [10]), MTA, Tempophore paste [6], 15.5–20% ferrous sulfate solution (Landan, Gohnsen, 1989, Fei et al, 1991), laser [15], recombinant human bone morphogenesis proteins (Nakashima, 1991; [14], Alberts et al, 1997), electrosurgical method (Ruemping, Moron, 1983; Mack, Dean, 1993), partial pulpotomy method [6–16]. Some of them (formocresolpulpotomy, tempofor-pulpotomy) have been tested in our country in recent years, and their acceptable effectiveness in the short and long term has been shown [1, 2, 4, 5]. When treating pulpitis of permanent teeth with incomplete root formation, it is important to create conditions for apexogenesis, which are provided by methods of indirect pulpothrapy, direct pulp coverage, vital partial and cervical pulpotomy, deep amputation of the pulp using a calcium hydroxide-based drug as a pulp-covering agent, and recently - Aggregate Trioxide Mineral (Mahmoud Torabinejat, 1995, 1998, 2001). At the same time, the clinical effectiveness of vital methods largely depends on the knowledge and experience of the doctor, the accuracy

of the technique of performing the method, the absolute isolation of the surgical field, and the patient's behavior. Therefore, at present, methods of devital amputation and extirpation in pulp therapy of temporary teeth, as well as devital pulp extirpation in permanent teeth with completed root formation in children, remain the methods of choice. Many years of experience in use indicate that, if the indications and technology are followed, the methods demonstrate good long-term treatment results. This message is devoted to devitalizing and mummifying agents used in the treatment of dental pulpitis in children, presented on the Belarusian market. Indications for devital amputation of the pulp of temporary teeth are: 1 acute partial serous pulpitis (extremely rare) (acute pulpitis according to ICD-C, 1995); 1 acute general serous pulpitis (acute pulpitis according to ICD-C, 1995); 1 chronic fibrous pulpitis (chronic ulcerative pulpitis, chronic pulpitis according to ICD-C, 1995); 1 chronic hypertrophic pulpitis (chronic hyperplastic pulpitis according to ICD-C, 1995); 1 exacerbation of chronic pulpitis without symptoms of acute periodontitis. Contraindications: 1 acute purulent pulpitis (purulent pulpitis according to IKBS, 1995); 1 acute and exacerbation of chronic pulpitis with symptoms of acute periodontitis; 1 chronic gangrenous pulpitis (pulp gangrene according to ICD-C, 1995); 1 X-ray changes in bone tissue in the area of the root furcation or apical part; 1 internal resorption of the tooth root(s). Indications for devital pulpectomy or pulp extirpation of temporary teeth are: 1 acute purulent pulpitis (purulent pulpitis according to IKBS, 1995); 1 chronic gangrenous pulpitis (pulp gangrene according to ICD-C, 1995); 1 acute or exacerbation of all forms of pulpitis with symptoms of acute periodontitis; 1 chronic or exacerbation of chronic pulpitis with radiological signs of changes in bone tissue in the area of the root furcation or the apical part of the root / roots of the tooth. It is believed that the most optimal treatment for pulpitis in children is the use of arsenic-free devitalizing agents, the main active ingredient of which is paraformaldehyde. When applied topically, paraformaldehyde affects the endothelium and smooth muscle of the capillaries and small blood vessels of the pulp, necrotic changes develop, exudative-inflammatory reactions are suppressed, and pulp mummification occurs. Theoretically, the root pulp remains fixed and sterile, thereby minimizing the risk of infection spreading into the periapical tissues and the likelihood of internal tooth root resorption. One of the commercial devitalizing agents presented in recent years on the Belarusian

dental market is the drug Depulpin from VOCO (Germany). Depulpin paste (Fig. 1) in its composition is a classic form of devitalizing agent. It contains paraformaldehyde, lidocaine hydrochloride as an anesthetic agent and filler. Depulpin paste is used for devitalization of the dental pulp before amputation or extirpation, as well as for final devitalization after removal of the coronal pulp of the tooth under anesthesia or in case of incomplete devitalization of the root pulp of the tooth. To devitalize the pulp, the drug is applied without pressure to the opened tooth cavity, after which it is hermetically sealed with a temporary dressing that prevents the drug from leaking or the release of formaldehyde. The duration of action of the devitalizing paste is on average 10–15 days; in case of residual manifestations of pulp viability, the application can be repeated after removing already devitalized fragments. The company Septodont (France) presents two drugs on the market that can be used in the treatment of pulpitis in children. These are caustinerf potent without arsenic (Fig. 2) and caustinerf pedodontic (Caustinerf fort sans arsenic and Caustinerf Pedodontic sans arsenic) (Fig. 3). Kaustinerv arsenic-free contains: trioxymethylene - 46.0; lidocaine - 37.0; fibrous filler - 100.0. Caustinerv pedodontica contains: trioxymethylene - 18.0; lidocaine - 36.0, parachlorophenol - 8.0, camphor - 13.0, fiber filler - 100.0. Both drugs contain trioxymethylene, an antiseptic whose coagulant effect on albumin is now well known. Lidocaine, with its local anesthetic effect, reduces the risk of a painful reaction. Parachlorophenol contained in caustinerva pedodontica in combination with camphor enhances the antiseptic effect of the drug, which is accompanied by effective sterilization, which completely eliminates the risk of infection of deeper tissues. When working with caustinervae, it is important to remember the need for the drug to come into contact with the dental pulp. You should very carefully open the tooth cavity, without excessive pressure, apply the caustinerv rolled into a ball directly onto the exposed pulp, and close it without pressure with a temporary filling. The next visit is planned in 7–10 days. In this case, the pulp, as a rule, acquires a fibrous structure and is very easily removed. Unfortunately, this processing technique is sometimes difficult to use and direct contact with the pulp cannot always be achieved. In this case, it is necessary to proceed in two stages. Direct contact with the pulp can be achieved in the second stage after pulp vitality has decreased. The company VladMiVa (Russia) presents two devitalizing agents on the market that can be used in the treatment of pulpitis in children. These are Devit-P and Devit-S. Devit-S (Fig. 4) contains paraformaldehyde, lidocaine hydrochloride and fiber filler. Devit-P - paraformaldehyde, lidocaine hydrochloride, chlorophenol, camphor, menthol, which can enhance its antiseptic properties. The preparations are intended for devitalization and mummification of the pulp of temporary teeth in cases where extirpation can be avoided, as well as for devitalization of permanent formed teeth in children in cases where vital methods cannot be used for various reasons. Complete devitalization of the pulp with Devit-P and DevitS pastes occurs within 3–5 days, in rare cases - 7. The second visit is planned within the time frame, according

to the recommendation of the manufacturer of the devitalizing drug. In the absence of complaints, the final preparation of the carious cavity, opening of the tooth cavity, and amputation of the coronal pulp are carried out. With adequate devitalization, the dental pulp at the mouths of the root canals has the appearance of gray-white tissue. A mummifying paste is applied over the mouths of the root canals. For a long time, PTEO paste (paraform, thymol, eugenol, zinc oxide) was used, which was prepared *ex tempore* before use. Currently, as an alternative to the mummifying paste PTEO, you can use Cresopate (Fig. 5) and Tempophore pastes from Septodont (Fig. 6), Cresodent from VladMiVa (Fig. 7). Cresopat paste contains parachlorophenol and zinc sulfate, which have pronounced antiseptic properties, and camphor, which “softens” the effect of phenol. The paste does not contain formaldehyde. Parachlorophenol has a microbicidal and microbostatic effect on all types of bacteria and complex viruses; the mechanism of its antimicrobial action is associated with the denaturation of microbial proteins. Cresodent paste has a similar composition. Tempofor paste contains iodoform, the antiseptic effect of which is complemented and enhanced by thymol and creosote. Tempofor has a bactericidal effect and is easy to use. It should be remembered that Tempofor tends to harden on the surface, especially when the jar is left open. Therefore, it is recommended to close the jar after each use; if necessary, stir the contents of the jar with a dry instrument before use. Due to the absence of formaldehyde in the above preparations and, as a consequence, the mummifying effect, high-quality preliminary devitalization and mummification of the root pulp is necessary. When treating pulpitis of permanent formed teeth after pulp devitalization, endodontic treatment is performed. If necessary, in case of incomplete devitalization of the root pulp, it is possible to re-use arsenic-free devitalizing agents at the mouths of the root canals.

Treatment of acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases in children

The prevalence of caries in children of the Republic of Belarus in various age groups ranges from 83 to 98% [3]. In the structure of inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region, 50% are odontogenic processes [5]. The prevalence of dental anomalies among children and adolescents is quite high - from 33 to 78% [1,4]. Despite the fact that these diseases are often the reason for surgical interventions, the structure of surgical interventions in a clinic has not been studied enough. At the same time, the study of the duration of outpatient treatment in children with acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases remains relevant. The purpose of the study was to study the structure of surgical interventions and determine the average duration of treatment for acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases in children on an outpatient basis. Operating logs and registers of patients sent for inpatient treatment were studied in the surgical room of the Republican Clinical Dental Clinic for the period from 01.2000 to 06.2003. 81 outpatient dental health records of children undergoing

emergency surgery for acute odontogenic inflammatory processes were studied. At the same time, the diagnosis and timing of postoperative treatment were recorded. The data were processed statistically using the Student's significance test. The total number of patients requiring surgical interventions during the study period was 721 (17.16 people/month). Of these, 600 children (14.28 persons/month) were operated on outpatient basis. Of the total number of outpatient operations, 268 (44.67±2.03%) were emergency surgical interventions for inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area. Statistically significantly more often such operations were performed on children with complicated caries - 207 (77.25±2.56%). 34 (12.69±2.03%) operations were performed for anomalies of the maxillofacial region, 25 (9.32±1.78%) operations for tumors and tumor-like formations, 2 (0.03%) operations for trauma. 71±0.51%). Planned (clean) operations were performed in 332 (46.05±1.86%). STRUCTURE OF REPLANNED OPERATIONS AND A LARGE NUMBER a t y s t i c a l reliably ($p < 0,001$) as emergency - 247 (92.16 ± 1.64%), and planned - 207 (62.35±2.66%) operations were performed on the soft tissues of the maxillofacial area. On the alveolar process, the number of operations was 21 (7.84±1.64%) and 125 (37.65±2.66%), respectively. Follow-up period 121 (16.78±1.39%) patient was sent to hospital treatment. For emergency reasons, 79 (65.00±4.51%) children were hospitalized. Of these, 17 (21.52±4.62%) were aged (children under 5 years old). The diagnosis was the reason for hospitalization for 36 (45.57±5.60%) patients. Other indications (non-contact with the patient, allergies to local anesthetics, general somatic diseases, etc.) were noted in 26 (32.91±5.29%) children. 42 (34.71±4.51%) children were hospitalized as planned. At the same time, according to age (up to 5 years), 16 (38.09±7.49%) children were sent to the hospital; in 9 (21.42±6.33%) cases, the cause of hospitalization was diseases not subject to treatment ulatory treatment, 17 (40.47±7.57%) children were hospitalized for other indications (non-contact of the patient, allergy to local anesthetics, general somatic diseases, etc.). As a result of studying outpatient dental health records, it was found that in a statistically significant majority of cases (82.71±4.20%), emergency outpatient operations were performed for acute purulent periostitis. Only 7 (8.64±3.12%) surgical interventions were performed for pericoronitis, 5 (6.17±1.08%) for suppurating dental cysts and 2 (2.48±1.72%) for suppurating radicular cysts. %). The overall average duration of treatment for children with odontogenic inflammatory diseases was 4.19±0.31 days. Treatment of acute purulent periostitis lasted an average of 3.72±0.31 days, pericoronitis - 2.00±1.77 days, suppurating tooth-bearing cyst - 8.60±0.78 and suppurating radicular cyst - 7.00±3.54 days. The duration of treatment for festering cysts was significantly longer than for periostitis and pericoronaritis. We have not identified any cases of complications during outpatient treatment of acute

odontogenic inflammatory processes. Thus, in the structure of outpatient surgical interventions in the maxillofacial area in children, planned (clean) operations prevail over emergency ones. A significantly larger number of emergency operations were performed for complicated caries, and planned operations for dental anomalies. The obtained data on the average duration of outpatient treatment of acute odontogenic inflammatory processes in children are comparable with the generally accepted treatment periods [2]. The absence of complications indicates the adequacy of the surgical treatment, and the high percentage of emergency surgical interventions for complicated caries may be associated with insufficient motivation of patients and their parents for planned sanitation of the oral cavity. Emergency hospitalization significantly prevails over planned hospitalization, while the indication for emergency hospitalization was mainly a dental diagnosis, while planned hospitalization in most cases was carried out for other indications.

References:

1. Kozlovskaja L.V., Jagur M.N., Burak Zh.M. // M-ly V s#ezda stomatologov Belarusi. — Brest, 2004. — S. 63–65.
2. Kozlovskaja L.V., Jagur M.N., Burak Zh.M. // Ctomatologicheskij zhurnal. — 2005. — №4. — S. 29–32.
3. Mahmud Torabindzhad. // Dent Art. — 2001. — №2. — S. 41–44.
4. Jacuk A.I., Mihajlovskaja V.P., Vasilenko E.P. // Sovrem. stomatologija. — 2004. — №2. — S. 42–44.
5. Jacuk A.I., Mihajlovskaja V.P., Mel'nichenko Je.M. // Sovrem. stomatologija. — 2000. — №2. — S. 42–43.
6. Bove C., Dermant L. //ASDT. Dent.Child. — 1982. — V.49. — R. 191–196.
7. Svek M. et al. // J. End. — 1982. — V.8. — R. 391–397.
8. Fei F., Udin R.D., Sisbin M. et al. // Pediatr. Dent. — 1991. — V.13. — R. 327–332.
9. Forabintjad M. // J. End. — 1995. — V.21. — R. 109–121.
10. Heilig G., Yoctes G., Sibsini M. et al. //J. Amer. Dent. Assoc. — 1984. — V.108. — R. 775–779.
11. Jepsen S., Albers M.K. // J. Endod. — 1971. — V.23. — R. 378–385. 1
2. Mack R.B., Dean J.A. //ASDC. J. Dent. Child. — 1993. — V.60. — R. 107–114.
13. Ruemping D.R., Morton T.N., Anderson M.W. // Pediatr. Dent. — 1983. — V.5. — R. 14–18.
14. Ruterford R.B. et al. //Arch. oral. Biol. — 1993. — V.38. — R. 571–576.
15. Shoj S., Nakamura M., Horiuchi H. // J. End. — 1985. — V.11. — R. 379–384. 16. Stefencohen M.A., Richard C., Burns. Pathways of the pulp. Ed.6.St.Louis, 1994.